

CNN BASED LEAF DISEASE IDENTIFICATION AND REMEDY RECOMMENDATION SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT:

Agriculture is one field which has a high impact on life and economic status of human beings. Improper management leads to loss in agricultural products. This process is to detect the leaf disease detection using the deep neural network the alternative of conventional neural network. This can easily detect the disease of leaf. First user can upload the image of leaf and it will upload the image on the screen. Then analyse the image by pressing the button. The disease can analyse and show the status of leaf that is healthy or unhealthy. The disease can be detected in the image of leaf. This work utilizes an open dataset of 1500 pictures of unhealthy and solid plants, where deep convolution system and semi supervised techniques are used characterize crop species and detect the sickness status of 3 distinct classes.

INTRODUCTION:

System analysis is the process of separation of the substance into parts for study and implementation and detailed Examination. It must be needed to keep the structured approach, which can be classified into four stages. The first is the investigation and understanding of the current physical system. It is a process of planning a new business system or replacing an existing system by defining its components or modules to satisfy the specific requirements. Before planning, you need to understand the old system thoroughly and determine how computers can best be used in order to operate efficiently. The next stage is to determine how the current system is physically implemented. The third step is the required logical system. Finally the required system can be developed. The system is performed by analyzing.

LITERATURE SURVEY

Title: The boosting approach to machine learning: An overview" in Nonlinear estimation and classification.

Author: R.E.Scahpire

Methodology

Boosting is a general method for improving the accuracy of any given learning algorithm. Focusing primarily on the AdaBoost algorithm, this chapter overviews some of the recent work on boosting including analyses of AdaBoost's training error and generalization error boosting's connection to game theory and linear programming; the relationship between boosting and logistic regression extensions of AdaBoost for multiclass classification problems; methods of incorporating human knowledge into boosting; and experimental and applied work using boosting

Advantage

They have several advantages over parametric classifiers such as discriminate analysis. The advantage of this work is to compare the performance of all three neural networks on the basis of its accuracy, time taken to build model, and training data set size.

Disadvantage

The most common problem in the Field of automatic diagnostic is the diagnostics using fast and accurate algorithm which doesn't require long time to run and give accurate and correct results.

Title: Support vector clustering

Author: A. Ben-Hur, D. Horn, H. T. Siegelmann, V. Vapnik

Methodology

Data points are mapped by means of a Gaussian kernel to a high dimensional feature space, where we search for the minimal enclosing sphere. This sphere, when mapped back to data space, can separate into several components, each enclosing a separate cluster of points. We present a simple algorithm for identifying these clusters. The width of the Gaussian kernel controls the scale at which the data is probed while the soft margin constant helps coping with outliers and overlapping clusters. The structure of a dataset is explored by varying the two parameters, maintaining a minimal number of support vectors to assure smooth cluster boundaries.

Advantage

A unique advantage of our algorithm is that it can generate cluster boundaries of arbitrary shape, whereas other algorithms that use a geometric representation are most often limited to hyper-ellipsoids

Disadvantage

We do not compute the whole adjacency matrix, but only adjacencies with support vectors.

Title: Land cover change assessment using decision trees support vector machines and maximum likelihood classification algorithms

Author: J. R. Otukey, T. Blaschke

Methodology

Land cover change assessment is one of the main applications of remote sensed data. A number of pixel based classification algorithms have been developed over the past years for the analysis of remotely sensed data. The most notable include the maximum likelihood classifier (MLC), support vector machines (SVMs) and the decision trees (DTs). The DTs in particular offer advantages not provided by other approaches. They are computationally fast

and make no statistical assumptions regarding the distribution of data. The challenge to using DTs lies in the determination of the “best” tree structure and the decision boundaries.

Advantage

A unique advantage of our algorithm is that it can generate the classification process by SVM,DT.

Disadvantage

We don't get the correct accuracy for the process.

Existing System

The effectiveness of the system depends on the way in which the data is organized. In the existing system, much of the data is entered manually and it can be very time consuming. When records are accessed frequently, managing such records becomes difficult. Therefore organizing data becomes difficult. The major limitations are:

- Even though advanced Machine Learning (ML) techniques have been adopted for leaf detection, the disease remains a major role in the leaf.
- Most of the existing ML-based leaf disease detection approaches are under two categories: supervised and unsupervised.
- In the existing system the leaf can be not detected in image processing.
- Only the disease can be predicted not the remedies can be predicted.

Disadvantage:

- Not correctly disease can be predicted
- Loss of information
- There is no remedy to clear the disease

Proposed System:

- The proposed model is introduced to overcome all the disadvantages that arise in the existing system.

- This system will increase the accuracy of the disease detection and it will show the remedy to overcome the disease.
- It enhances the deep convolutional neural network will increase the performance.

Advantages:

- High performance.
- Provide accurate prediction results.
- Reduces the information Loss
- It can verify the image in dataset

Flow Diagram:

A **data-flow diagram** (DFD) is a way of representing a flow of a data of a process or a system (usually an information system). The DFD also provides information about the outputs and inputs of each entity and the process itself. A data-flow diagram has no control flow, there are no decision rules and no loops. Specific operations based on the data can be represented by a flowchart.

There are several notations for displaying data-flow diagrams. The notation presented above was described in 1979 by Tom DeMarco as part of Structured Analysis.

For each data flow, at least one of the endpoints (source and / or destination) must exist in a process. The refined representation of a process can be done in another data-flow diagram, which subdivides this process into sub-processes.

The data-flow diagram is part of the structured-analysis modelling tools. When using UML, the activity diagram typically takes over the role of the data-flow diagram. A special form of data-flow plan is a site-oriented data-flow plan.

Data-flow diagrams can be regarded as inverted Petri nets, because places in such networks correspond to the semantics of data memories. Analogously, the semantics of transitions from Petri nets and data flows and functions from data-flow diagrams should be considered equivalent.

Usecase Diagram:

While a use case itself might drill into a lot of detail about every possibility, a use-case diagram can help provide a higher-level view of the system. It has been said before that "Use case diagrams are the blueprints for your system". They provide the simplified and graphical representation of what the system must actually do.

Due to their simplistic nature, use case diagrams can be a good communication tool for stakeholders. The drawings attempt to mimic the real world and provide a view for the stakeholder to understand how the system is going to be designed. Siau and Lee conducted research to determine if there was

a valid situation for use case diagrams at all or if they were unnecessary. What was found was that the use case diagrams conveyed the intent of the system in a more simplified manner to stakeholders and that they were "interpreted more completely than class diagrams".

The purpose of the use case diagrams is simply to provide the high level view of the system and convey the requirements in laypeople's terms for the stakeholders. Additional diagrams and documentation can be used to provide a complete functional and technical view of the system.

Class Diagram:

In software engineering, a **class diagram** in the Unified Modeling Language is a type of static structure diagram that describes the structure of a system by showing the system's classes, their attributes, operations (or methods), and the relationships among objects.

The class diagram is the main building block of object-oriented modeling. It is used for general conceptual modeling of the structure of the application, and for detailed modeling translating the models into programming code. Class diagrams can also be used for data modeling. The classes in a class diagram represent both the main elements, interactions in the application, and the classes to be programmed.

In the diagram, classes are represented with boxes that contain three compartments:

- The top compartment contains the name of the class. It is printed in bold and centered, and the first letter is capitalized.
- The middle compartment contains the attributes of the class. They are left-aligned and the first letter is lowercase.
- The bottom compartment contains the operations the class can execute. They are also left-aligned and the first letter is lowercase.

A class with three compartments. In the design of a system, a number of classes are identified and grouped together in a class diagram that helps to determine the static relations between them. With detailed modeling, the classes of the conceptual design are often split into a number of subclasses.

In order to further describe the behaviour of systems, these class diagrams can be complemented by a state diagram or UML state machine.

Sequential Diagram:

A sequence diagram shows object interactions arranged in time sequence. It depicts the objects and classes involved in the scenario and the sequence of messages exchanged between the objects needed to carry out the functionality of the scenario. Sequence diagrams are typically associated with use case realizations in the Logical View of the system under development. Sequence diagrams are sometimes called **event diagrams** or **event scenarios**.

A sequence diagram shows, as parallel vertical lines (*lifelines*), different processes or objects that live simultaneously, and, as horizontal arrows, the messages exchanged between them, in the order in which they occur. This allows the specification of simple runtime scenarios in a graphical manner.

ER-Diagram:

An **entity–relationship model** (or **ER model**) describes interrelated things of interest in a specific domain of knowledge. A basic ER model is composed of entity types (which classify the things of interest) and specifies relationships that can exist between entities (instances of those entity types).

In software engineering, an ER model is commonly formed to represent things a business needs to remember in order to perform business processes. Consequently, the ER model becomes an abstract data model, that defines a data or information structure which can be implemented in a database, typically a relational database.

Entity–relationship modeling was developed for database design by Peter Chen and published in a 1976 paper. However, variants of the idea existed previously. Some ER models show super and subtype entities connected by generalization-specialization relationships, and an ER model can be used also in the specification of domain-specific ontologies.

Architecture Diagram:

MODULE DESCRIPTION:

DATA SELECTION AND LOADING

- The image can be selected first and upload in the page.
- In this project, the leaf disease dataset is used for detecting the disease.

- This dataset contain the image of disease leaf and no disease image leaf. The dataset contain all type of leaf.

DATA PREPROCESSING

- This step is to verify the image that uploads in the process.
- In this verify image, the image can be verified by image color, image path of directory and image size.
- So this process can verify that the image is normal or blur .The clarity of image can be verified here.

Conclusion:

Convolution neural network is used to detect and classify plant diseases. The Network is trained using the images taken in the natural environment and achieved 99.32% classification ability. This shows the ability of CNN to extract important features in the natural environment which is required for plant disease classification.

Image classification, Image Categories, Feature Extraction, and Training Data is carried out. The whole development of algorithm is done in Python tool. Using several toolboxes like Statistics and Machine Learning toolbox, Neural Network Toolbox and Image Processing Toolbox the outputs as of now are the training data in form of image categories, image classification using K-Means clustering and moisture content along with predicting of withstanding. The algorithm

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